

DIPLOMA

TA'LIM FIDOYILARI

RESPUBLIKA ILMIY JURNALIDA

G.M. Toychieva

SIGNIFICANCE OF "COACHING" METHODOLOGY

NOMLI MAQOLASI BILAN ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN TAQDIRLANADI

Bosh muharrir:
A.A. Abdurahmonov

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★ ★ ★ ★ ★
HONORED
MENTION
★ ★ ★ ★ ★

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